

ETYMOLOGY OF SOME FOOD NAMES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article deals with the etymology of some food names in English and Uzbek languages. Although English and Uzbek languages are rich of types of food, hardly any people are aware of where their names have come from.

In this work etymology of food names and their meaning will be analyzed in both languages.

Key words: Pudding, Crumpet, Bangers and Mash, Shepherd's Pie, Haggis, Manti, Mastava, Palov, Lag'mon.

The number of people drawn to the possibility of studying the origin of food names has been rising at an alarming rate over the past few decades. The most well-known scientists in our nation have made a significant contribution to the growth of this area. For instance, candidate of philological sciences Gulnoza Odilova worked on the topic "Dunyo adabiyotida "taom" va "tavovul" mavzusi which contributed a lot to the origin of food names. Furthermore, "Suyuq ovqat nomlari ishtirok etgan paremalarning etnolingvistik tadqiqi " by Y.U.Nurova play an essential role in the development of the field related to the etymology of some food names.

There a great number of food names in English language. I have given some examples and their origin.

Pudding – is considered as a part of main meal that can be a dessert or a spicy food. The term "pudding" is thought to have its origins in the Latin word "botellus," which means "little sausage" and may have given rise to the French word "boudin," which originally referred to the encased meats that existed in medieval European puddings. One more comes from the West German word "pud," which means "to swell." The word "pudding," according to the Oxford English Dictionary, dates to the thirteenth century. It describes the stomach or entrails of a sheep, pig, or other animal that have been filled with meat, suet, oats, and seasonings.

Crumpet – goes as far back as 17th century; possibly from cromptid cake (literally, "curled-up cake," a wafer) or from cromptid, a variant of crumpen (literally, "to curl up"). A different etymology is Celtic; see Welsh crempog and Breton krapouezh ("crepe, pancake"). Sense of "attractive woman" first used in 1936; it may have been a cockney rhyming slang term for strumpet; alternatively, see tart ("loose woman, prostitute"), which may have been a heart or darling in its own right.

Bangers and Mash - Even though it's commonly claimed that the phrase "bangers" dates back to World War II, it was really in use as early as 1919. The word "bangers" is said to have originated in the UK because, during World War I, when there was a lack of meat, sausages were created with a huge water content that made them prone to popping under high heat when cooked.

Shepherd's Pie - "Cottage-Pye" is mentioned numerous times in Parson Woodforde's diary entries from 29 August 1791 onward. He notes that the meat was veal but omits to mention the topping. It has been used frequently, though not exclusively, for dishes of chopped or

minced beef with a mashed potato topping in the 20th century and afterwards. Beef can be cooked before or after being fresh; the latter was once more common. Due to the lack of refrigeration well into the 20th century, many residential kitchens found it more convenient to preserve cooked meat than raw meat. When housewives bought their Sunday meat, the chef Louis Diat recalled in the 1940s, "they selected chunks huge enough to put into leftover dishes for some days."

Haggis – the name of this food goes as far back as late middle English from “hag” or “haggen” which means chopping or mincing, a traditional Scottish dish that is typically eaten with neeps and tatties (mashed swede and potatoes) and whisky. It is made from minced sheep offal, oats, spices, and other ingredients. It was traditionally boiled in a sheep's stomach.

Uzbek language is also full of types of food. There are a few examples of them and their meaning:

Mastava – comes from the Persian language which means “most” – “sour cream” and “ob” – “water”. In fact, Mastava soup is prepared by boiling rice in the whey obtained from yogurt. Now Mastava is prepared from carrots, onions, rice and other ingredients. According to the taste and method of preparation, there are such types as boiled, fried, cherry, minced, khorda. (leek is added instead of rice). The main type of Mastava is prepared by boiling mutton mince: small balls are made with minced meat mixed with onion and pepper. The bone separated from the pulled meat is boiled in a cauldron, and after it is cooked, the bones are drained and boiled with rice and rounded balls in the soup. You can also add onions, tomatoes, diced carrots, potatoes or turnips. Mastava is strained into bowls, sprinkled with coriander and pepper and brought to the table. Yogurt is served in a separate bowl.

Manti – is a dish consisting of thinly sliced meat inside a thin spread of dough made with the help of steam. This dish is a traditional meat dish of the peoples of Central Asia, Turkey, Mongolia, Korea, Tatarstan, Crimea. The word manti is believed to be derived from the Chinese word "mantou".

Palov – this word comes from the first letters of ingredients which are used for this meal. They are : P- piyoz (onion), A- ayoz-sabzi (carrot), L-laxm-go'sht (meat), O- olio-yog' (oil), V- vet-tuz (salt). It is divided into different types according to its taste and preparation method, and it is prepared in a different way in each country. The basis of the dish is rice. In addition to this ingredient, oil, meat, carrots, onions and other ingredients are used. Pilaf is popular mainly among the peoples of Central Asia and the Middle East in terms of preparation and distribution. For example, in Uzbekistan, Uzbek pilaf is considered one of the main dishes of Uzbek cuisine and is loved in every household, at weddings and in other countries of the world.

Lag'mon – comes from the Uygur word “la myan” that means stretched dough. A dish prepared by stretching the cooked dough. After the dough is cooled, it is wrapped to rest for 1 hour. The dough is kneaded and baked, and Lagman dough is rolled out of it by hand. Cooled vegetable oil is smeared on the face so that the Lagman does not stick to each other. Put the dough in boiling salted water and cook it until it floats to the surface. The cooked dough is rinsed in cold water. Meat, bell pepper and onions, carrots, radishes, cabbage, tomatoes, garlic, potatoes, etc. are chopped to prepare cabbage, and onion are finely chopped. Meat, onion and garlic, bell pepper, tomato is fried in the stained oil, and water is poured with radishes, potatoes and shallots.

To conclude, while working on this article, I have come across very useful facts behind food names. Their names are suitable their preparation, origin and ingredients. Despite the fact that some names have been used as Uzbek and English words, their etymology depends on other nations.

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